

EFL Teachers' Practices and Constraints in Implementing the Reflective Approach to Teaching Writing in Grade 11 in Addis Ababa City, Ethiopia

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of this study was to investigate teachers' practices and challenges in implementing the reflective approaches to EFL classes with particular reference to five selected secondary schools in Addis Ababa. The study had three research questions and employed a descriptive qualitative research design, involving eleven grade 11 English language teachers. Empirical data were collected through semi-structured interviews and document analysis. The findings indicated that though grade eleven English teachers are qualified enough to implement the reflective approach to teaching writing, the data confirmed that they could not apply it to the real classroom situations as frequently as possible due to several pulling and pushing factors. The majority of them used direct feedback and meta-linguistic feedback. The salient challenges that hindered the implementation of this approach to writing classes were the English teachers' in-bred beliefs that were transferred from their predecessors, large class size, students' low capacity in the writing skills, lack of sufficient time for teachers to reflect on each student' written work, students' low appetite to learn from the reflections they received from their English teachers and students' lack of commitment to improve their writing skills through their own efforts.

Key words: Reflection, Reflective approach, Teaching writing, Teachers' written feedback

1. INTRODUCTION

The English language pedagogy nowadays has made a major paradigm shift from the traditional, teacher-centered and top down methods to an approach that is flexible and democratic. Such an approach has the potential to define teaching in its own terms (Richards & Lockhart, 2007). English as a foreign language (EFL) classes require an atmosphere which is conducive to practice language skills freely and imaginatively. In this regard, reflective teaching is in harmony with this approach and enables teachers to constantly reflect on their classroom practice.

John Dewey was the pioneering founder of reflective thinking, which is the basis of reflective teaching. Various scholars (Ghaye, 2011; Lyons, 2010; Pollard et al., 2014) claim that reflective thinking has been accepted as one of the strategies to developing teachers' reasoning capacity about why they employ any instructional approach and how they can improve their teaching. Dewey (1933) was of the view that teachers should be given the platform so that they can become contemplative and problem solvers who not only transfer knowledge but also investigate their experience and reflect technically and critically in different ways. In the same way, Rodgers (2002) briefly discussed Dewey's four principles of reflection. Firstly, reflection is a process whereby learners are motivated to make meanings by having a deeper understanding of the connections and relationships to other experiences and thoughts. Secondly, reflection is a well-organized, thorough, and systematic, methodical way of thinking which is inherent in scientific studies. Thirdly, reflection should take place in community where interaction with others is indispensable. The last principle is that reflection requires mindsets that value the intellectual and personal development of oneself and of others.

Researchers agree that the reflective approach (RA) to teacher development offers advantages for personal and professional development. From this perspective, Richards (2002) claimed that teacher development should not be viewed as a task but rather a continuous process where the teacher is engaged in exploring his or her own teaching through reflective teaching in a collaborative process. This view is also encapsulated in various Ethiopia's Ministry of Education documents. A case in point is the Ministry's teacher's portfolio document which explains that teachers should be constantly exploring new and improved ways to develop their students' understanding. Additionally, they should try out and evaluate, revise, and reflect on their teaching strategies constantly, always taking into account the ways how their students learn (Ministry of Education, 2009).

There is no question about the importance of reflection in the Ethiopian educational system. The practice of reflection should be the task that students take responsibility. For example, it is stated in the Ethiopian curriculum framework document that students should be taught to take ownership of their learning, become motivated and challenged, take risks, learn from their mistakes and from one another, and be confident in expressing their views and doing things independently, construct and co-construct meanings from knowledge and experiences (Ministry of Education, 2020). Therefore, this can be taken as evidence that teachers must be not only reflective of their teaching practice but also empower learners to develop the skill of reflection.

The Ethiopian continuous professional development (CPD) framework defines good teaching when a teacher is reflective about his/her classroom practice (Ministry of Education, 2009). In relation to this, Ng et al., (2004) emphasize that teachers, as reflective practitioners, are expected to carry out reflection through critical thinking, drawing from a variety of sources including their own classroom practices. In a similar vein, critically reflective teaching happens when practitioners identify and analyze the assumptions that shape their practice (Brookfield, 2017). Therefore, reflective teaching equips teachers with the necessary skills to creatively mediate external requirements (Pollard et al., 2014).

Reflective teaching has won acclaim throughout the world in improving the students' language skills, especially that of writing (Bolton, 2010; Lyons, 2010). Scholars agree that writing is a multi-faced language skill that can be learnt through continuous effort and getting appropriate feedback from English teachers or peers (Zeraatpishe & Azarnoosh, 2018).

According to Taczak and Robertson (2017), there is a perceived understanding that reflection is a very important element in writing sessions, and that students are required to reflect so that they can make improvements in their writing. Ariana (2010) argues that writing skills have the capacity to help learners organize their thoughts in a meaningful manner. Besides,

they assist the learner to process information in their mind correctly, enabling them to write independently, comprehensibly, fluently, and creatively.

The process of writing suggests that the students are taught how to write with coherence, acceptable spelling, and appropriate grammar structure (Freedman et al., 2014 as cited in Hussain, 2017). The other dimension is to look at the learners in the process of writing when they are given a task to do an assignment. Very often, the quality of an assignment depends on the conditions under which it was written. Observing students during writing can give some important insights into these conditions and the learners' control over parts of the writing process (Nation & Macalister, 2010). Activities focusing on these areas provide an opportunity for students not only to think about the specific requirements of reflective writing as a distinct genre, but also to practice the writing and thinking skills involved (Lyons, 2010). Therefore, reflective writing can serve as a powerful tool for students' learning (Burton et al., 2009).

Nowadays, the inclination of most writing teachers is to use the process approach to writing instruction (Mesfin, 2013). According to this school of thought, writing is taught freely in such a way that the students pass through different stages of writing. The role of the students is to select their own titles, generate ideas, produce the first draft, and carry out editing, reviewing and writing the final copy. On the other hand, the role of the teacher is to prepare students for self-evaluation in the form of reflection and make process writing an indispensable component part of the students' writing experiences (Lee, 2017).

Regarding the implementation of the reflective approach, some studies have been conducted by (Berhan, 2019; T. B. Dereje, 2009; Dutamo and Assefa, 2022) in the Ethiopian context. However, they mainly focused on pre-service trainee teachers and teacher educators' reflective practices at tertiary level. Other local research works were also carried out by Dereje et al. (2017) and Amera (2016); Gudeta (2022) though their studies were conducted at primary and secondary education levels respectively. They did not specifically investigate the implementation of the reflective approach in teaching writing.

This study, however, differs from all mentioned above. First, the focus of its attention is studying the practices and challenges in implementing the reflective approach in teaching writing. In addition, there has been no study on the implementation of a reflective approach to the teaching of writing in the context of secondary schools in Addis Ababa. Therefore, this research is original in its own right.

2. RESEARCH QUESTIONS

The main aim of this study is to investigate Grade 11 English language teachers' practices and challenges in implementing the reflective approach in their writing classes. To achieve this, the study attempts to answer the following research questions:

- 2.1** What are the practices of grade eleven English teachers in implementing the reflective approach to teaching writing?
- 2.2** Do the pieces of feedback grade eleven English teachers provide to their students on their writing give emphasis to reflective approach?
- 2.3** What challenges do grade eleven English teachers face in implementing the reflective approach to teaching writing?

3. LITERATURE REVIEW

3.1 The Concepts of Reflection, Reflective Practice and Reflective Teaching

Various scholars have defined the concepts related to 'reflection'. However, there is no a one-size-fits-all definition. For example, Ghaye (2011) is of the opinion that definitions of reflection should revolve around issues that centre the individual's internal thought processes and responsibility for their actions' rather than on the wider, social context of one's practice.

When seeing reflection through the lens of philosophy and education, Dewey (1933) defined the term as a cognitive inquiry in which experiences are analyzed in the context of prior knowledge for the endeavors of finding meaning that will lead to the creation of a new knowledge and to the development of new alternative ways. Moon (2013) sees reflection on a different lens. She believes that reflection is a process that lies somewhere around the concept of learning and thinking. She further notes that practitioners reflect in order to learn something, or they learn as a result of reflecting. Therefore, 'reflective learning' as a concept, emphasizes the intention to learn resulting from reflection.

Dewey made a distinction between reflective thought and a random 'stream of consciousness', highlighting that the latter is thought that we experience on an ongoing basis. He defined reflection in broad terms as 'active, persistent, and careful consideration of any belief or supposed form of knowledge in the light of the grounds that support it and the further conclusions to which it tends' (Dewey, 1933). Bolton (2010), on the other hand, defined reflection as a state of mind, an ongoing constituent of practice, not a technique, or curriculum element. In education, Dewey recognized that it is important to focus on enhancing problem-solving and critical thinking skills rather than just rote memorization of contents (Gupta, 2019).

Reflective practice has become a popular concept in the late 1900s and into the twenty-first century (Barnett & O'Mahony, 2006). It incorporates a variety of features including: problem setting and solving; the development of analytical skills and attitudes that facilitate reflection, such as self-awareness and self-determination; the examination of values, moral principles and ideological and institutional constraints (Davison & Dowson, 2009). Furthermore, reflective practice can enable practitioners to learn from experience about themselves, their work, and the way they relate to home and work, significant others and wider society and culture (Bolton, 2010). Consequently, in order to become and remain effective, professional language teachers should engage in reflective practice. In other words, one of the key skills for effective language teachers in the 21st century, along with their knowledge, experience, and expertise, is the ability to consistently reflect on their teaching practices (Farrell, 2015).

Ghaye (2011) asserts that wherever there is reflection there is practice as they are inseparable. He upholds the view that reflections provide fresh insights and deeper understanding, guiding us to enhance our actions and decisions. Okech (2008) concurs that reflective practice may lead to either more or less intimate co-leader interactions depending on the quality and depth of the intrapersonal and interpersonal processes involved in the practice. However, Russell (2005) voiced his concern that the lack of a clear consensus on the definition of reflective practice and its recognition contributes to the uncertainty around how to effectively teach it.

As noted by Richards and Lockhart (2007), reflective language teaching is an approach that second language teachers use to 'collect data about teaching, examine their attitudes, beliefs, assumptions, and teaching practices, and use the information obtained as a basis for critical reflection'. For Dewey, reflective teaching is viewed as knowledge generating and justifying thinking in light of evidence is an important criterion for reflective thinking (Lyons, 2010). Therefore, reflective teaching fosters both foundational training in schools and ongoing professional development for primary and secondary teachers throughout their careers. (Pollard et al., 2014)

3.2 Levels of Reflection

Scholars have different views regarding levels of reflection. For example, Geetha (2020) believes that reflection-in-action and reflection-on-action are the two major integral parts of self-reflection. Schon (1983) distinguishes them to explore how individuals utilize their experiences to assess their practices. He explained that reflection-in-action involves the iterative process of evaluating the series of actions taken during an activity for continuous

improvement, while reflection-on-action entails logically contemplating the overall outcome of that activity.

Schon (1983) described reflection-in-action as ‘thinking on our feet.’ It involves looking at our experiences, connecting with our feelings, and attending to our own theories. It entails building new understandings to inform our actions in the situation that is unfolding. When teachers engage in reflection-in-action, they attempt to consciously stand back while they are teaching as they monitor and adjust to various circumstances that are happening within the lesson. This includes reflecting on how the students are responding or not responding, how long each activity may be taking and/or how individual students are interacting with the content of the lesson (Farrell, 2015).

Ghaye (2011) succinctly described ‘reflection-on-action’ as a deliberate, conscious and public activity mainly designed to improve future action. When teachers engage in reflection-on-action, they are examining what happened in a lesson after the event has taken place and this is a more delayed type of reflection than the reflection-in-action (Farrell, 2015). Both forms of reflection contribute immensely to improve the capabilities of a reflective teacher (Pollard et al., 2014)

Scholars discussed a third dimension to reflection which is viewed as ‘reflection-for-action,’ This kind of reflection is mainly related to taking some measures to do something with what the practitioner has learned (Ghaye, 2011). Furthermore, when teachers engage in reflection-for-action, it means that they are attempting to reflect before anything has taken place and expect what may happen before they conduct the lesson (Farrell, 2015)..

3.3 Teacher Written Feedback

Teacher written feedback is inherently related to classroom tasks and assessments. For example, classroom writing assessment becomes more effective if it helps students to learn better and make them better writers (Lee, 2017). Teachers, first and foremost, should have good familiarity with the capacity of their learners. As noted by Pollard et al.(2014) effective teachers usually update themselves to align themselves with the current understanding and overall capacity of the learner. Feedback, though is not the only means, can be utilized as one powerful answer for the effectiveness of strategies employed by teachers (Hattie, 2009). By the same token, researchers such as (Lyons, 2010; Pollard et al., 2014) indicate that effective learning can take place when there is early and constructive feedback. Effective feedback, therefore, can be aligned with effective teaching if it provides sufficient information about students performance in relation to the goals they set (Lee, 2017).

The process approach to the teaching of writing sees the learner as the main producer of the texts and teachers are expected to provide uninhibited feedback (Hyland, 2004). Second language writing teachers spend over one third of their time providing feedback (Lee, 2017). Nonetheless, teachers find it lengthy and difficult to apply this approach in the classroom because they have to provide constructive individual feedback during the entire writing process (Zeraatpishe & Azarnoosh, 2018)

In a reflective approach to the teaching of writing, feedback plays a crucial role for encouraging students to reflect in every writing process. Hattie (2009) notes that one of the most important and a measurable result of such teaching strategy is to give relevant and appropriate feedback to students. This strategy creates an opportunity for students to see how their teachers respond to them so that they can learn from their responses (Hyland, 2004). Therefore, the feedback provided by teachers can occur in two forms: positive or negative. The positive aspect can be utilized to boost motivation, provide a positive learning environment and inform students how well they accomplished writing tasks (Richards & Lockhart, 2007).

Hyland (2004) argues that teacher written responses play a central role in most second language writing classes. Written feedback can be provided in one of two ways: either by

underlining or circling an error or recording in the margin the number of errors in a given line (Bitchener & Ferris, 2012). The responses can include three major areas '(a) an indication that an error has been committed, (b) provision of the correct target language form, or (c) meta-linguistic information about the nature of the error, or any combination of these' (Ellis et al., 2006).

Scholars categorize feedback into two: direct and indirect feedback. Bitchener and Ferris (2012) made a distinction between the two and explained that direct feedback offers an explicit correction of linguistic form or structure above or near the linguistic error. On the other hand, indirect feedback pinpoints an error but it does not offer a correction or explicit meta-linguistic information (Lee, 2017). Proponents of the indirect feedback argue that this approach serves two purposes, the first one is by creating spacious space for allowing reflection and the second one is concerned with enhancing long-lasting acquisition of the skill (Bitchener & Knoch, 2008).

In conclusion, despite the debate over which approach is effective, the indirect approach to providing feedback can help the learner to engage in 'long-term acquisition and written accuracy' (Bitchener & Knoch, 2008). In addition, the feedback provided by the teacher should gear towards improving students' writing by allowing them to adopt a self-inquiry approach where they can reflect on their strengths and weaknesses (Lee, 2017).

4. METHODS

4.1 Design of the Study

This study focused on exploring the implementation of the reflective approach in grade eleven writing classes in Addis Ababa. To achieve the methods, the researchers opted to use the descriptive qualitative research design. This design was chosen due to the fact that the research questions stipulated in this study call for data that require deep analysis and interpretations. Yin (2016) argues that the main goal of qualitative research is to gather sufficiently rich data that allows for a comprehensive understanding of the context surrounding the events under investigation.

4.2 Sampling and Procedures

The participants in this research were eleven grade eleven English teachers drawn from five secondary schools in Addis Ababa, the capital of the federal government. To this end, eleven teachers were selected to participate in the interview. Selection of the participants was made using purposive sampling based on some set criteria such as willingness to participate in the research, gender representation and varied teaching experience. In a similar vein, three students' written texts were selected for document analysis using simple random sampling technique.

4.3 Data Collection Instruments

The research tools employed for data collection included semi-structured interviews and document analysis. The specifics of each instrument are outlined below.

4.3.1 Semi-structured Interviews

The interview questions for grade eleven English language teachers were prepared in English. Accordingly, a total of eleven grade eleven English language teachers were selected. Selection of the interview participants was made on a voluntary basis. Accordingly, twelve semi-structured interview items were prepared based on the research questions and review of related literature.

The researchers interviewed the teachers. The interviews were carried out on an individual basis. All the participants unanimously chose English to be the language of the interview. They also signed a consent form to confirm their willingness to participate in this study.

4.3.2 Document analysis

The researchers of this study collected some essays of students' works to examine the type of feedback provided by teachers. To this end, a document analysis was conducted. According to Bowen (2009), document analysis requires the data to be "examined and interpreted in order to elicit meaning, gain understanding, and develop empirical knowledge".

4.4 Data Analysis Procedure

A thematic analysis was employed to analyze the qualitative data. Thematic analysis is a method predominantly used to analyze qualitative data that includes searching across a data set to identify, analyze, and report repeated patterns (Braun & Clarke, 2006). Accordingly, the data from semi-structured interviews were first transcribed manually. Then the transcribed data were coded. The coded data were then categorized into different groups. After that, the grouped data were converted into themes. The themes were further broken down into sub-themes. Finally, each sub-theme was analyzed against the research questions presented in this study.

With regard to document analysis, students' compositions were collected from three teachers and the analysis was conducted using clearly set criteria from the existing theories and the literature review. Some of the criteria were informed by Ferris and Hedgcock (2005) guiding principles of written commentary.

4.5 Ethical Considerations

Right from the inception of this study, ethical approval was obtained from Hawassa University. Besides, the researchers assured confidentiality for participants. In analyzing the data, codes were used for the entire participants instead of mentioning their names. The researchers also confirmed that the participants could withdraw at any time.

5. RESULTS

5.1 Results of the Data from the Interview

As a way of making the participants familiar with the content of the interview items, the first part of the questions mainly focuses on the demographic data of the teachers. In presenting the description, interpretation, and discussion of the data in the interview, the researchers used the following codes:

ET1---English language teacher one (any of the interviewees who is coded number1).

ET2 --English language teacher two (any of the interviewees who is coded number2), etcetera

English Teachers	Sex	Qualification	Years of Experience
ET1	M	MA in TEFL	Between 11 and 20 years
ET2	M	MA in TEFL	Between 11 and 20 years
ET3	M	BA in TEFL	Between 5 and 10 years
ET4	F	MA in TEFL	Between 11 and 20 years
ET5	F	MA in ELT	Between 5 and 10 years
ET6	M	MA in TEFL	Above 20 years
ET7	M	MA in TEFL	Between 11 and 20 years
ET8	F	BA in TEFL	Between 11 and 20 years
ET9	M	BA in ELL	Between 11 and 20 years
ET10	M	MA in TEFL	Above 20 years
ET11	M	MA in TEFL	Between 11 and 20 years

Table 1 presents information about the English language teachers who were interviewed for this study. The data display that 8 (73%) of them were master's degree holders whereas 3

(23%) of them had bachelor degrees. The table shows that all have specialization either in teaching English as a foreign language (TEFL) or English language teaching (ELT) or English language and literature (ELL). The table also discloses that two, seven and two teachers interviewed had more than 20, between 11 and 19 and between 5 and 10 years of teaching experience in secondary schools respectively. This implies that the writing lessons are taught by adequately qualified English teachers. Therefore, it is possible to check the extent to which they give attention to reflective teaching which requires them to apply a variety of questioning strategies, manage the process of teaching writing, provide constructive feedback and evaluate improvements from time to time.

Teacher	No. of workshops	Topic	Remark
ET 1	One	General	Summer training using RA as one approach
ET 2	Two	Teaching free writing	Summer training using RA as one approach
ET 3	Two	Teachers as reflective practitioners	Summer training using RA as one approach
ET 4	None	-----	-----
ET 5	One	General	Summer training using RA as one approach
ET 6	None	-----	-----
ET 7	One	General	Summer training using RA as one approach
ET 8	One	General	Summer training using RA as one approach
ET 9	None	-----	-----
ET 10	One	General	Summer training using RA as one approach
ET 11	One	RT and student centred approach	-----

The data in the above table depicts that six of the interviewees attended one workshop whose focuses were on Reflective Approach in different years. Meanwhile, three interviewees had no opportunity to participate in any workshops, while the other two gained theoretical and practical knowledge through various other means. The data further indicate that teachers do not have the exposure to attending workshops and training that are tailored to ‘reflection’ or ‘reflective teaching’ or the reflective approach’. Most of them noted that they have got some knowledge of the concepts during the summer training which was organized in 2024. On top of that, the participating teachers pointed out that the summer training gave them some insights as to what the reflective teaching approach looks like.

The following table allocates the themes emerged from semi-structured interview data that address the research questions.

Code	Major Themes
Theme 1	Teachers’ Understanding of the Concept of Reflection
Theme 2	Applying the Reflective Approach in Writing Classrooms
Theme 3	Types of Feedback Provided by Teachers
Theme 4	Challenges to Implement the Reflective Approach in Writing Classes

Theme 1: Teachers’ Understanding of the Concept of Reflection

This theme focuses on getting the overall perception of teachers regarding the concept of ‘reflection’. Accordingly, though the way they express it differently, they have a common denominator on the perception of the concept. For all the teachers, the understanding of ‘reflection’ revolves around issues related to providing feedback, evaluating one’s

performance, making suggestions, and insights on students' work. Especially, the perception of ET9 is quoted as follows:

Reflection is a process by which we ask ourselves such questions as 'Did I teach in a proper manner?' 'Did I use the appropriate teaching methods?' 'Were my students active?' 'What were my strengths?' (ET9).

Similarly, ET 1 gave their perception about the concept of reflection in the following manner: As the term implies, reflection means self assessment. As teachers we usually assess ourselves on what we have done. We reflect to evaluate ourselves or we can define reflection as a process of seeing oneself in the mirror. We can also conduct assessment of other's work in the process of reflection. (ET1).

From the results given above, it is possible to suggest that the perception the English teachers held is somehow ideal and reasonable. Consequently, we can say that they have some understanding of the concept which may help them to implement it in teaching writing despite the challenges they are to confront.

Theme 2: Applying the Reflective Approach in Writing Classes

The second theme refers to how teachers apply the reflective approach in their writing sessions. When the respondents were asked the question whether or not they apply the reflective approach in their writing sessions, almost all of them agreed that they implement it rarely. When the researchers asked them the reason, they stated that most of their students prefer direct corrections to reflective feedback on their writing. The second reason was that there are a large number of students who cannot reflect on other students' writing. Third, reflection requires getting training and having sufficient time and knowledge in the content area. Thus, most of the time they ask the students to produce different texts and then either they take them home, correct them by themselves or distribute them to the class and allow them to evaluate based on the criteria they write on the black/whiteboard.

Theme 3: Types of Feedback Provided by Teachers

The third theme focuses on the types of feedback given by teachers. From their responses, the interviewees explained that they give both oral and written feedback. They pointed out that the main reason for giving oral feedback is the fact that the time allotted for writing skills is so insufficient that they address only the most common issues focusing on writing accuracy rather than fluency. In addition to this, most of the teachers give direct written feedback. When students make mistakes, the common practice of the teachers is to underline the part (s) where the error (s) occurs and they write the correct version on it. They pointed out that they also give general comments, which include capitalization, spelling, tense, coherence of ideas and use of cohesive devices

Theme 4: Challenges to Implement the Reflective Approach in Writing Classes

Table4: Challenges EFL Teachers Face in Implementing the Reflective Approach	
Types of challenges	Codes of teachers identified the challenge
Student related	ET1, ET2, ET3, ET4, ET5, ET6, ET7, ET8, ET10, ET11
Teaches related	ET1, ET2, ET3, ET4, ET5, ET6, ET7, ET9
Time related	ET1, ET2, ET6, ET9, ET10
Class size related	ET4, ET5, ET7, ET11
Writing skill related	ET1, ET2, ET9, ET10
Materials related	ET3, ET6, ET10

The last theme is concerned with the challenges teachers face in implementing the reflective approach in writing sessions. In their response to the item that asked the participants about the challenges they face in implementing the reflective approach to the teaching of writing,

the most dominant listed ones are the following: The first challenge has to do with students. The interviewees indicated that several students have low command of the English language due to their background in primary and middle schools. The second challenge raised by the participants is related to teachers. Teachers' knowledge gap of theories as well as the current trends and practices of the reflective teaching approach coupled with lack of interest immensely affects its implementation. The third challenge is attributed to time. Time constraint in covering the writing content affects its proper implementation. The fourth challenge is to do with large class size. They indicated that the reflective approach requires a limited number of students in the classroom because the English teacher has to reach out to each student and stand at his/her side to manage the writing progress, supervise his/her performance, bridge his/her gaps and evaluate his/her progress. The fifth challenge is related to the nature of the writing skill itself. In this regard, ET 2 noted that the very nature of the writing skill by itself is challenging. It requires commitment and continuous practice on the part of the student. The last one is related to the teaching and learning materials that are being used in the schools. ET 6 voiced the concern that the textbook are so bulky that teachers themselves are forced to focus on content coverage rather than conducting critical reflection.

5.2 Results of the Document Analysis

The researchers made analysis of three sample pieces of writings. The analysis is based on five established criteria. The focus of the analysis is mainly evaluating the feedback given by the teachers in relation to whether the feedback was provided in the form of reflection so that students could improve their writing skills.

Sample Written Feedback 1

In the first sample written feedback, the teacher gave their comments in simple and clear language although they are packed with several phrases or sentences inside the students' writing or on the lower margin of the paper. The teacher also concerned with the left and right margins of the paper. The teacher drew two zigzag lines as borders never to be crossed. The teacher also indicated 'layout' issue by directing the student in an arrow.

As we delve deeply into the teacher's reflection on the students' writing, the teacher provided feedback on places where they thought the student made errors. To this end, there are many additions and corrections to the students' original work. The corrections mainly focus on punctuation marks, capitalization and spelling. The teacher gave some meta-linguistic explanations. However, no attempt was made to help students reflect on their strengths and areas of improvement. The teacher made a suggestion to split the paragraph into two by looking at the length of the text. From this one can infer that the focus is heavily on form and format rather than meaning. Therefore, teachers should create a platform for self-reflection so that students can do better in subsequent writing tasks.

Sample Written Feedback 2

In the second sample written work, the teacher reflected their views on the student's writing clearly and briefly. The teacher gave one correction by inserting the infinitive marker 'to' in the third line. Notwithstanding, the teacher overlooked other erroneous sentences.

One of the positive aspects in this sample text is that the teacher adopted a holistic approach in providing feedback, categorizing into strengths and weaknesses. However the teacher's comments were mainly on the surface issues such as grammar and punctuation marks. The meaning aspect was neglected. Such kind of feedback may not help the students set their own goals.

Sample Written Feedback 3

This sample writing task is concerned with writing a dialogue. The teacher reflected his/her views clearly and briefly. The teacher made an attempt to suggest to the student in a less constructive manner. The teacher also asked the student the following questions "Whose

mother is she?” “Why do you want to interview her?” “You must describe her at the beginning”. In spite of this, the teacher marked the sentences where the student made no grammatical mistakes as a sign of encouragement.

Upon closely examining the feedback, the teacher made appropriate corrections on two occasions where the student used the ampersand (&) in place of ‘and’. In a similar vein, the teacher circled the misuse of the verb ‘go’. The teacher should have given additional feedback that could enhance the content of the writing task. In light of this, the feedback provided by the teacher did not help the student to reflect on his/her strengths and weaknesses. Therefore, it is imperative that teachers improve the skill of providing feedback. Ferris and Hedgcock (2005) argue that providing feedback is a skill and it can be developed through practice and reflections

6. DISCUSSION

This study examines the practices and challenges of Grade 11 English language teachers’ implementation of the reflective approach in writing classes. This section discusses the implication of the research findings in relation to the three research questions.

6.1 Teachers Practices in Reflecting on their Students’ Writing

The first research question was to investigate the practices of Grade 11 English teachers in implementing the reflective approach in writing classes. The findings derived from the interviews provided significant information about the teachers reflective practices. In general, all the teachers offered their perceptions, which laid the foundation for understanding their practice. The results of the interviews suggested that the teachers had some awareness of the concept of reflection in general and shared their reflection based on their own experience and theory perspectives. There is no a one-size-fits-all definition of the term ‘reflection’ in the literature, which is also reflected in the interviews with the teachers. In this regard, Ghaye (2011) advises that practitioners should not worry about finding the perfect definition for the concept of ‘reflection’. Therefore, teachers have the autonomy to construct their own meanings. According to Hyland (2004), a strong teacher is someone who not only engages in reflection but also associates classroom tasks with relevant research and theory. As Lyons (2010) pointed out the problems pertaining to understanding the concept of reflection still persist.

A close examination of the data in this study disclosed that most of the participating teachers had the perception that they implemented the reflective approach rarely. In line with the perception, their practices indicate that they do not frequently apply reflective teaching method. This finding seem to be consistent with the study conducted by Gudeta (2022) who claimed that teachers still use the traditional teacher centered method as opposed to the reflective approach.

6.2 Teachers’ Feedback in Enhancing Reflection

The second research question was about whether or not the feedback provided by the teachers to their students on their writing gives emphasis to the reflective approach. The findings were derived from document analysis. The results of the study disclosed that the teachers used direct feedback, meta-linguistic feedback and provided some or no comments. The study also found that the teachers’ reflective practices are also mirrored in the feedback they gave to the students’ written tasks. This finding matches with the finding of Hakimi (2020) who conducted empirical and analytical research on teacher’s feedback approach in a high school EFL class in the Moroccan context. The study found that teachers relied heavily on form-focused feedback. Such practice inhibits students from seeing their weaknesses and strengths. This may result in de-motivating students. Richards and Lockhart (2007) argue that teachers’ feedback should play a more positive role by increasing motivation and building a supportive classroom climate. Therefore, it is advisable to bring to the attention of the problems attached

to students' composition works rather than simply providing direct feedback (Bitchener & Ferris, 2012)

6.3 Challenges in Applying the Reflective Approach on Students' Writing

The third research question is related to the challenges teachers face in applying this approach in their classes. The data obtained from the interview suggested that student-related challenges were significant. The interviewees indicated that several students have low command of the English language due to their background in primary schools. This finding is consistent with the finding of Dutamo and Assefa (2022) who claimed that students' poor writing skills in previous grades contributed to this predicament. Teacher-related challenges are also the most prominent ones. The findings of this study revealed that teachers' knowledge gap is the main inhibitor for fully implementing the method. A similar finding was reported by Jemadi et al., (2023) who stated that English teachers' lack of knowledge about reflective teaching is the major barrier to practice reflection.

This study found out that large class size plays a deterrent role in fully applying the method. This result matches with the findings of Bahanshal (2013) who also found out that large classes pose huge difficulties in teaching writing effectively. The study found that time constraint is the other potential impediment that stifles the effective implementation of the approach. This finding is also echoed in the study conducted by Dereje et al., (2017) who stated that having less time for reflection is one of the stumbling blocks for applying reflective teaching in EFL classes. Finally, the study found that the very nature of the writing skill is the other most notable challenge in the teaching of writing. Barkaoui (2007) reviewed research and theories in connection with second language writing. He indicated that several factors related to developing a positive attitude towards writing, language competence, thinking abilities and socio-cultural are attributed to this hurdle.

7. CONCLUSION

The study revealed the status of teachers' reflective practices and the challenges they faced with respect to implementing the reflective approach to teaching writing. It is revealed from the findings that Grade 11 English language teachers are well aware of the benefits and contributions of the reflective approach to teaching writing. Nevertheless, most of the teachers did not apply it in teaching writing. The study also disclosed that the English teachers did not have wide opportunities to participate in workshops, seminars and in-service training which can essentially contribute to updating their awareness of approaches to the teaching of English language skills in general and the writing skill in particular. Contrary to the above findings, as the data from the interview and document analysis showed, most grade 11 English teachers were implementing the reflective approach to teaching writing in the process of feedback provisions. The study also showed that teachers' practices of written feedback mainly focused on error correction. Implementation of such strategies could not help students to reflect on their strengths and weaknesses, hindering them to improve their writing skills. It is concluded from the study that there are multifarious challenges in implementing the reflective approach in grade 11 writing classes. The challenges are students' background of English, teachers' inbred beliefs about the teaching methods which they inherited from their predecessors, the class size, , time constraints to provide timely feedback, both oral and written, to the students' written materials and the very nature of the writing skill itself.

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Declaration of competing interest

We would like to declare that there is no conflict of interest in relation to this study.

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This study was approved by the Ethics Committee of Hawassa University with Ref. No. CSSH/121/24. Furthermore, written consent was obtained from all research participants.

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